

Introducing Digital Humanities in Library and Information Centers: Ensuring Ethical Responsibility of Library Professionals

Subhajit Panda* and Navkiran Kaur**

Digital Humanities (DH) is a rapidly growing field that brings together scholars from a wide range of disciplines to explore the intersection of human culture and technology. DH leverages the power of digital tools and methods to study and analyze various aspects of human culture, including literature, history, art, and language, and has the potential to transform the traditional methods of organizing, managing, and disseminating information. This paper presents an all-inclusive exploration of DH and its application in Library and Information Centers (LICs). It further examines the challenges and benefits of incorporating DH into information management methods and the most effective practices for its implementation. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of ethical considerations when working with DH. Through this, LICs can remain relevant and responsive to the needs of their users while adhering to ethical standards.

The rise of digital technologies has brought about significant changes in the ways Library and Information Centers (LICs) operate. With the digitization of resources and the growing importance of digital literacy, library and information professionals are increasingly looking to incorporate Digital Humanities (DH) into their work. This has led to the emergence of DH as an interdisciplinary field (Klein, 2015, p. 10) that combines traditional humanities with computer science, data analytics, and other digital tools (Anderson, 2022, p. 9). It is a field that uses computational tools and methods to study human experience and culture. DH has transformed the way scholars, researchers, and students interact with information, opening up new avenues for research, analysis, and dissemination (Pawlicka-Deger, 2021). However, as library professionals move towards this new field, they must also ensure that they are behaving in an ethical and responsible manner.

* Assistant Librarian, Chandigarh University, Gharuan, Mohali (Punjab) and Researcher, Department of Library and Information Science, Punjabi University, Patiala (Punjab). E-mail: suvapanda007@gmail.com

**Assistant Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, Punjabi University, Patiala (Punjab). Email: navkiran_lis@pbi.ac.in

This paper aims to provide an overview of DH and its application in LICs, discuss the benefits and challenges, explore best practices for implementation, and ensure ethical considerations are taken into account.

The concept of digital humanities, commonly referred to as DH, emerged in the early 2000s as a progression of the “Computation in the Humanities” project that began in the 1950s. While there is no universal definition of DH, it is generally understood as a collaborative and interdisciplinary approach to generating and analyzing digital data through computational processing within the humanities disciplines (Gonzalez & Rodrigues, 2022). In other words, DH involves the use of digital technologies to enhance and transform traditional humanities research and scholarship. Over the years, the field has grown to encompass a wide range of disciplines, including history, philosophy, linguistics, and cultural studies. DH has become an essential tool for researchers, providing them with innovative ways to approach and analyze their subject. The following literature review provides a critical analysis of the relationship and cooperation between Digital Humanities (DH) and libraries.

Russell (2011) presented the challenges encountered by developers of DH resources and how libraries could help overcome these. Sula (2013) situated digital humanities work within the user-centered paradigm of library and information science and developed a cultural informatics model of libraries. DH. Zhang et al. (2015) proposed present and future roles for LIS professionals in DH projects and examined effective ways for libraries and information centers to collaborate with the DH community. Ferguson et al. (2016) reported on a research project investigating the ethical dilemmas experienced by library and information professionals, and the contribution case studies can make to ethical understanding and decision-making.

The literature also highlighted the diverse skills, knowledge, and experience exhibited by librarians in the digital humanities. Millson-Martula and Gunn (2017) published a special issue of *College & Undergraduate Libraries* that discussed current challenges in digital

humanities. Risam et al. (2017) examined work creating DH opportunities for underserved student populations at Salem State's Berry Library, serving as a model for building DH at regional comprehensive universities. Kamble (2019) explored the relationship of library and information professionals with digital humanities and effective ways to support DH education and research, while Millson-Martula and Gunn (2020) showcased the range of projects and theoretical issues tackled by academic librarians, including DH pedagogy and collaboration. Yao and Xiao's (2022) study revealed the varied roles of DH librarians and emphasized the importance of collaboration, clear frameworks, and resource investment for successful DH pedagogy.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that libraries need to stay up-to-date to remain relevant in the digital age. It offers insights into the relationship between libraries and digital humanities, the evolving role of LIS professionals, collaboration with the DH community, and ethical issues. Case studies are recommended to educate practitioners. The literature also highlights the growing expertise of librarians in DH and their potential to support underserved student populations.

The scope of this paper is to explore the role of Digital Humanities in LICs. It highlights how DH is transforming the traditional methods of organizing, managing, and disseminating information in libraries and information centers. The objectives of this paper are:

- i) to provide an overview of Digital Humanities (DH) and its application in LICs,
- ii) to discuss the benefits and challenges of using DH in LICs,
- iii) to explore some of the best practices for implementing DH in LICs, and
- iv) to ensure ethical consideration while introducing DH in LICs

Digital Humanities in Library and Information Centers

This section of the paper is structured into three sub-sections to explore Digital Humanities (DH) in libraries comprehensively. The first sub-section provides an overview of DH and its tools and methods, such as text mining, network analysis, and visualization. The second sub-section discusses the benefits and challenges of using DH in libraries and how it transforms traditional information management

methods. The third sub-section explores best practices for implementing DH in libraries, emphasizing the significance of collaboration, training, and support for DH projects.

Digital Humanities and its Application in LICs

Digital Humanities is an interdisciplinary field that combines traditional humanities research with digital tools and methods. It encompasses a wide range of research and scholarship, including text analysis, data visualization, network analysis, and digital publishing. Further, this rapidly growing field has the potential to revolutionize the way in which LICs manage their collections and serve their users. There are numerous applications of DH in LICs, including:

Data Analysis and Visualization

DH provides libraries with powerful tools for analyzing and visualizing their collections. For example, the New York Public Library's Map Warper project allows users to overlay historical maps onto modern-day maps to see how cities and landscapes have changed over time (The New York Public Library, 2012). This type of analysis and visualization can provide insights into historical and cultural trends that might otherwise be difficult to discern.

Digital Preservation

DH provides LICs with innovative ways to preserve and digitize cultural artifacts and data. For example, the British Library's Endangered Archives Program (EAP) works with libraries and archives around the world to digitize and preserve at-risk materials, such as manuscripts, photographs, and sound recordings (British Library, 2004). By using DH tools and techniques, the EAP is able to digitize these materials and make them accessible to a wider audience.

Collaborative Research

DH encourages collaboration between researchers from different disciplines, which can lead to new insights and discoveries. For example, the Digital Public Library of America (DPLA) is a collaborative effort between libraries, museums, and archives to provide digital access to their collections (DPLA, 2019). By working together, these institutions are able to provide a more comprehensive view of American history and culture.

Text Mining

DH provides libraries with powerful text-mining tools that can help analyze large amounts of data

quickly and efficiently. For example, the HathiTrust Digital Library contains millions of digitized books that can be searched and analyzed using text-mining tools (HathiTrust Digital Library, 2019). This type of analysis can help researchers identify patterns and trends that might otherwise go unnoticed.

Network Analysis

DH provides libraries with powerful tools for network analysis, which can help analyze the relationships between different entities in a collection or dataset. For example, the Stanford Literary Lab has used network analysis to explore the relationships between different characters in works of literature (Stanford Literary Lab, 2023). This type of analysis can provide new insights into the structure and meaning of literary works, as well as other types of cultural artifacts.

Benefits of Using Digital Humanities in LICs

Digital Humanities can bring many benefits to LICs, including making cultural heritage materials more accessible, enabling new research methods and new insights, and facilitating collaborations between researchers and institutions.

Wider Accessibility of Cultural Heritage

One of the main benefits of DH in LICs is the ability to make cultural heritage materials more accessible to a wider audience. By digitizing and making available these materials online, libraries can reach new users and promote scholarship and research in new and innovative ways.

Innovative Pedagogy

DH can also be used to support innovative pedagogy, by providing students with hands-on experience working with digital tools and datasets. For example, students can use DH tools to analyze primary source materials or develop their own digital projects, such as online exhibits or interactive maps.

Professional Development

DH can also provide opportunities for professional development for library professionals. By learning new digital tools and techniques, library professionals can expand their skill sets and develop new competencies.

Facilitate Collaboration between Researchers and Institutions

Another benefit of DH is that it allows for collaboration between institutions and researchers. DH projects often involve interdisciplinary teams with diverse skill sets, including researchers, librarians, archivists, and technologists. This can lead to new and

innovative approaches to research and scholarship, as well as to the creation of new tools and resources that benefit the wider community.

Preservation and Archiving

DH can help LICs preserve and archive their collections for future generations. Digital preservation can help ensure that digital materials are accessible and usable over time while archiving LICs can develop strategies for managing and preserving their collections in perpetuity.

Challenges of Using Digital Humanities in LICs

However, there are also challenges to implementing DH in LICs, including technical and financial constraints, the need for training and expertise, and issues related to copyright and intellectual property.

Lack of Technical Expertise and Resources

One of the main challenges is the need for technical expertise and resources. Many DH tools and methods require specialized knowledge and infrastructure, such as high-performance computing resources and large-scale data storage. Implementing these technologies can be expensive and time-consuming.

Intellectual Property and Copyright Issues

Another challenge is related to intellectual property and copyright issues. DH projects often involve the digitization and dissemination of materials that are still under copyright. This can create legal and ethical challenges, as libraries must balance the need to make materials accessible with the need to respect the rights of copyright holders.

Despite these challenges, DH is transforming the traditional methods of organizing, managing, and disseminating information in LICs. DH tools and methods enable LICs to create new forms of knowledge, promote new research methods, and reach new audiences. As DH continues to evolve, it will undoubtedly play an increasingly important role in the work of libraries and other cultural institutions.

Best Practices for Implementing Digital Humanities in LICs

Implementing Digital Humanities in LICs can be a complex and challenging process, requiring careful planning and implementation. Here are some best practices for implementing DH in libraries that highlight the importance of collaboration, training, and support for DH projects:

Collaborate with Other Institutions

Collaboration is key to successful DH projects. LICs should consider partnering with other institutions, such as universities, museums, or archives, to share resources and expertise. Collaborating with other institutions can also help to increase the impact and visibility of DH projects.

Invest in Training and Support

DH projects require specialized skills and expertise, and it is important for libraries to provide training and support for staff members. This can include training in digital tools and methods, as well as in project management and data management. LICs should also consider providing ongoing support for DH projects, such as technical assistance and project management advice.

Start Small

LICs should consider starting with small DH projects, which can help to build skills and expertise before taking on larger, more complex projects. This can also help to demonstrate the value of DH to stakeholders and build support for larger projects down the line.

Engage with Users

LICs should engage with users throughout the DH project, from the planning stages to implementation and dissemination. This can include conducting user needs assessments, soliciting feedback and input, and engaging users in the creation of digital tools and resources.

Prioritize Data Management

DH projects often involve the creation and management of large amounts of data, and it is important for libraries to prioritize data management throughout the project. This can include establishing data management plans, using open data standards, and ensuring the long-term preservation and accessibility of data.

Ethical Responsibility Associated with Digital Humanities

Ethics is an important consideration in Digital Humanities projects, particularly from the perspective of LICs and librarians. Some key ethical considerations in DH include:

Privacy is a key concern in DH projects, particularly when it comes to the use of personal data. Libraries and librarians must ensure that they

are collecting and using personal data in a way that is transparent and respects individuals' privacy. This may include obtaining informed consent from users and ensuring that data is stored securely.

Intellectual Property is another important ethical consideration in DH projects. Libraries and librarians must ensure that they respect copyright and other intellectual property laws when digitizing and disseminating materials. This may include obtaining permission from copyright holders or using materials that are in the public domain.

Access is another ethical consideration in DH projects. Libraries and librarians must ensure that the digital resources they create are accessible to a wide range of users, including those with disabilities or who do not have access to the internet. This may include providing alternative formats or using open data standards to ensure that the resources can be easily accessed and used.

Libraries and librarians must also be mindful of issues related to *cultural heritage and the representation* of marginalized communities in DH projects. This includes ensuring that materials are digitized and preserved in a way that respects the cultures and traditions of the communities they come from, as well as ensuring that marginalized voices are represented in the digital resources created by DH projects.

Conclusion

Digital humanities are transforming the traditional methods of organizing, managing, and disseminating information in LICs. DH provides researchers, scholars, and students with innovative ways to approach and analyze their subject matter. While there are challenges to implementing DH in LICs, such as the need for collaboration, training, and support, the benefits of using DH in LICs are significant. As such, LICs must embrace DH to remain relevant and responsive to the needs of their users. However, it is essential that library professionals approach this field in an ethical and responsible manner. This includes respecting the privacy and intellectual property rights of users, as well as being transparent about how data is collected and used. As LICs continue to evolve in the digital age, it is vital that ethical responsibility remains at the forefront of all digital humanities work.

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